

Supporting Human-Robot Collaboration and Safety with the Proposed Explainable Neuro-symbolic Reasoning

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Abstract—In this article, we present an overview of the innovative architecture of the proposed hybrid AI approach for safety and anomaly detection in Human-Robot Collaboration environment. Firstly, we outline the problem and the proposed solution and its application to human-robot collaboration scenarios. Then, we discuss the performance of the approach proposed method for anomaly detection and its conformity to the requirements defined by the end-users in realistic scenarios.

I. INTRODUCTION

Currently, we can observe closer Human-Robot Collaboration (HRC) in various industrial and everyday use cases. Advancements in computer vision, robotics, and machine learning have generated new ideas and possibilities for various applications. While human-robot collaboration/interaction (HRC/HRI) applications enhance productivity, ensuring safety remains a critical challenge in the design and implementation of these systems. Of course, the major principle is not to hurt/harm humans by the operating robots.

In this context, there is a need to deploy intelligent mechanisms to detect various safety-related events and ultimately to increase the safety of the human operator and eventually to improve the trust in the robotic system. By detecting specific events or behaviors (e.g. anomalies in the execution of the industrial process), it is possible to reduce potential errors and improve the fluency of the entire process. However, the primary issue lies in effectively monitoring the interactions between human workers and robots while maintaining an adaptive and flexible system that can detect anomalies and safety-related events in real-time.

Therefore, in this paper we propose...

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows...

II. RELATED WORK

Modern robotics systems, especially those designed for human-robot collaboration (HRC), generate vast

amounts of structured sensory data. This data often comes in the form of ROS bag files, which record streams from various sensors such as LiDAR, RGB-D cameras, or odometry. To manage and analyze this data, the robotics community has developed dedicated tools for real-time visualization and debugging, with RViz¹, Foxglove Studio², and WebViz³ being among the most widely adopted solutions.

These tools allow the integration of multi-modal sensor data into a unified, interactive dashboard—typically in a 3D environment—which facilitates understanding how a robot perceives its surroundings. Web-based solutions like WebViz and Foxglove Studio, leveraging modern JavaScript libraries (e.g., React.js, Regl.js, Three.js), provide additional flexibility through modular dashboards and easier deployment (e.g., via Docker). In contrast, desktop applications like RViz remain tightly integrated with the ROS ecosystem and are limited primarily to Linux-based platforms. While these tools are powerful for visual debugging and situational awareness, they are mostly confined to the syntactic level of interpretation: they show what is happening, but not necessarily why.

At the same time, a parallel trend has emerged in robotics research—focused on the use of AI techniques to interpret human behavior and enhance autonomy in shared workspaces. In particular, HRC systems are increasingly expected to operate in socially acceptable ways, which requires them to understand human intentions, actions, and safety states [1]. This has led to a surge in methods centered around human motion recognition and pose estimation [2]–[4], often seen as a prerequisite for interpreting collaborative behavior.

Pose estimation can be performed in both 2D and 3D, and categorized into top-down and bottom-up

¹<http://wiki.ros.org/rviz>

²<https://foxglove.dev/>

³<https://webviz.io/>

approaches [5], [6]. While 2D methods rely solely on visual data, 3D estimation often integrates complementary sensor inputs, such as depth cameras, LiDAR, or IMU data. Recent models, like SeS-GCN [7], go further by forecasting future poses, enabling proactive and safe robot behavior.

These perception capabilities serve as a foundation for higher-level reasoning, particularly in safety-critical applications. An emerging challenge is anomaly detection in human-robot interactions—i.e., recognizing when something goes wrong based on multimodal behavioral data [8]. Traditional deep learning models offer impressive performance but often act as black boxes, making it difficult to understand or explain their decisions in real-time scenarios.

This leads us to a crucial observation: while traditional tools in robotics support rich visualization of sensor data, they do not address the interpretability and symbolic reasoning needs that arise with the use of modern AI techniques. As the field moves toward more intelligent and autonomous collaborative systems, the ability to explain decisions, detect semantic anomalies, and reason symbolically becomes critical.

To address this gap, we propose a novel neuro-symbolic AI approach that bridges low-level sensory data (e.g., ROS bag content) and high-level semantic reasoning. Our framework augments deep perception models with interpretable symbolic decision rules, providing both visual context and logical explanation of robot behavior. In the following sections, we present the details of this approach and demonstrate how it enables safer, more transparent collaboration between humans and machines.

III. CONCEPTUAL OVERVIEW OF THE PROPOSED APPROACH

Conceptual overview of the problem is shown in the figure 1.

The scene (Work Environment) consists of several elements, that are observed and sensed with various devices (depth cameras, robot sensors, etc.).

At the core of the system is the monitoring system (Hybrid AI Solution), which continuously processes data from multiple sources to detect relevant events and anomalies.

Whenever potential safety events/anomalies are detected, the system generates an alert that is sent to both the worker and the administrator. The worker, who is directly involved in the scene, can receive real-time warnings about possible risks, allowing them to take immediate action. The administrator, on the other hand, gains insight into system behavior, enabling them to assess broader safety trends and make necessary adjustments to improve detection accuracy.

In our case, as the anomaly, we consider one of the following events:

- Violation of safety guidelines (e.g., human standing with back facing to the robot, a person entering a restricted area).

- Interruptions in the assembly process (e.g., a human operator drops an item).
- Operators' safety signals (e.g. emergency stops body gestures).
- Anomalies in human and robot activities (e.g., unusual human behaviors reflected in activities or gestures).

Additionally, there are other technical challenges that impact the architecture of the hybrid AI solution. In particular:

- Limited time or feasibility of creating a comprehensive labelled dataset. As a result, the system should allow users to easily define detectable events without requiring a full retraining of the model. This should also account for cases where users can incorporate domain knowledge to improve detection accuracy and effectiveness. For example, if we know that a worker is in an area where the lower part of their body is occluded, any predictions related to that region should be treated with lower confidence or switched to other camera.
- Even with the limited amount of labeled data, the user should have the ability to fine-tune the system by incorporating expert knowledge. This poses the challenge of how expert knowledge can be incorporated into the system while still allowing traditional gradient backpropagation training to be used.
- Certain level of flexibility and modularity, which will ensure that adjustments to the observed scene (e.g. the number or positioning of cameras) require minimal effort for system to be re-deployed. In a result, this adaptability should be established upon a stable and universal set of expert knowledge. For instance, recognizing certain human behaviors or gestures can be possible regardless of camera's mounting position in the workshop.

IV. NEURO-SYMBOLIC APPROACH AS A HYBRID AI

By employing a hybrid neuro-symbolic AI approach to identify such events, our goal is to enhance the human operator's safety and ultimately improve trust in robotic systems. Neuro-symbolic AI is one of the key approaches within Hybrid AI⁴, combining the strengths of both symbolic reasoning and neural networks to enhance interpretability and adaptability. It is often said that the neural networks are good at recognizing patterns from large datasets but often are limited in providing transparency and require extensive labelled data for training. In contrast, symbolic reasoning is established on logical inference, domain knowledge integration, and rule-based decision-making. However, pure symbolic solutions struggle with learning from raw data.

⁴Bhuyan, B.P., Ramdane-Cherif, A., Tomar, R. et al. Neuro-symbolic artificial intelligence: a survey. *Neural Comput & Applic* 36, 12809–12844 (2024).

Fig. 1. Conceptual overview of the problem and the proposed solution.

Fig. 2. Example of the neuro-symbolic processing paradigm. The input image x is processed by the neural model M (parameterized by θ), which generates the structured input r for the logic program PP . Supervision is provided on y , meaning the system must learn θ without direct supervision on r .

The typical structure⁵ of the neuro-symbolic processing paradigm has been depicted in the figure below. In the presented diagram the logic program (P) and the neural model (M) play distinct roles in a neuro-symbolic learning framework.

The logic program (P) is designed to operate on structured input (r), which will be further explained in the next section. In our case, it is a concatenation of various observations accompanied with probabilities. In contrast, the neural model (M), which is parameterized by weights parameters θ , handles unstructured input x (in our case video, depth maps, sensory data, etc.).

A crucial aspect of this system is the supervision mechanism used during the learning (error backpropagation) process. For the neuro-symbolic approach the supervision is provided on y . It means that the system must learn θ without direct supervision on r . This aligns with the fundamental assumption for neuro-symbolic AI, where neural networks learn from raw data while symbolic reasoning ensures structured and interpretable decision-making.

V. PROPOSED ARCHITECTURE OF THE SOLUTION

The final architecture of the proposed solution has been depicted in the figure below. In contrast to previous version, the Hybrid AI module is no longer standalone component, but has been integrated with the

remaining part of the robotic workshop infrastructure adapting the ROS (Robot Operating System) framework. The solution has access to all the cameras and sensors deployed in the workshop. These are accessible via convenient publish-subscribe communication paradigm. The Hybrid AI module consumes the data throughout the predefined set of topics and produces structured outputs as ROS messages.

Internally, the Hybrid AI module combines the strengths of symbolic reasoning (which provides precise, human-understandable rules) with deep learning (which can extract complex patterns from data). Thanks to the hybridization of neural and symbolic approaches, it is possible to achieve low-level perception (e.g., images, robot sensory data) while enabling common-sense reasoning through probabilistic programs (symbolic reasoning). The pipeline realizing this has been depicted in the figure below.

The processing architecture that is illustrated in the diagram consumes video data (specifically images) along with sensor data. These are processed in parallel within various blocks depicted in the figure. Images first pass through the Backbone network (High Resolution Network - HRNet) and are then processed by the Human Pose Regression Head, which generates human body and pose parameters. These details are further analyzed in the Probabilistic Symbol Extraction Heads. Simultaneously, sensor data is also incorporated into this layer. The purpose of this layer is to generate probabilistic symbols. Each symbol is associated with a probability (therefore we call them probabilistic symbols), which are then passed to the Symbolic Program for further reasoning. More details on symbolic programs are provided in the following sections. However, the program generates predictions, which structure can vary depending on the program structure (e.g. it can be just an anomaly flag with the classification, or a categorization of the robot state, etc.).

⁵arXiv:2304.04812

Fig. 3. High-level overview of the solution. The Hybrid AI module has been integrated with the remaining workshop components using ROS (Robot Operating System) infrastructure.

Fig. 4. The overview of the hybrid model combining neural networks with symbolic programs.

Fig. 5. The neural part of the component followed by the symbolic program.

A. Deep neural network component

The neural network component consists of a human pose regression head, followed by several parallel processing symbol extraction heads. This has been depicted in the diagram below.

In principle, the final version of the architecture uses HRNet (High-Resolution Network) as a backbone and ROMP regression head for reliable and stable human 3D pose extraction and tracking.

The HRNet is a neural network designed to maintain high-resolution representations throughout processing.

Unlike traditional convolutional networks that progressively reduce resolution to extract features, HRNet keeps multiple parallel branches at different resolutions and continuously exchanges information between them. In HRNet32, the number 32 refers to the number of channels in the lowest-resolution stage within the hierarchical representation structure. This means that the lowest-resolution feature maps in HRNet have 32 channels.

The probabilistic symbol extraction heads include several independently processing pathways, each named according to its specific purpose.

Each head is implemented using two convolutional layers and one fully connected layer, with normalization in between. The conceptual diagram is shown in the figure below.

We use supervised training with image-level labelling. This means that each image is assigned a label indicating the event (e.g., human activity) without additional details. Moreover, we freeze the backbone network and ROMP weights while training the system.

Fig. 6. Probabilistic symbol extraction head structure. It is using two convolutional layers and one fully connected layer, with normalization in between.

Fig. 7. The steps for transforming a ProbLog program into an Arithmetic Circuit.

B. Symbolic component

The DeepProbLog⁶ engine was used to establish a foundation for symbolic analysis and to utilize it as a tool for defining expert and domain knowledge. However, we explicitly separated the system into two parts: the training phase and the inference phase. This separation was introduced to eliminate certain dependencies that posed challenges during deployment in the use case. Specifically, we ground and compile the DeepProbLog program directly into so-called Arithmetic Circuit⁷ to avoid dependencies on Prolog, and related operating system level libraries, which are essentially required in the previous release.

To integrate the ProbLog program as an element of the neural network model, it needs to be structured in a way that mimics the neural network's operation. In other words, the program must be expressed as a function (or a set of functions) that maps an input tensor to an output tensor. More precisely the process follows the steps shown in the diagram below.

We focused on extracting expert knowledge in the form of neuro-symbolic rules. As illustrated in the diagram below, these rules are divided into two main categories. The first category is connected to human-related aspects, allowing for the extraction of gestures, activities, and presence in specific areas of the workshop. The second category concerns the environment and the robots themselves, enabling the classification

of the robot's position, its current activity, and its correlation with a worker's activity, who is located in the same area as the robot. The rules implemented in symbolic programs can be broadly categorized into the following groups:

- Rules detecting gestures signaled by workers (e.g. hand signals).
- Rules identifying various workers activities (e.g. bending, squatting).
- Rules monitoring the state of the UAR-10 robot.
- Rules signaling the position of mobile robot (AMR) within specific areas.
- Rules indicating presence or absence of human worker within designated sectors of the workshop.
- Rules detecting unusual or incorrect human behavior, which may pose safety risks. These mostly focus on spotting such moments when human is within the robot's operational area or a person is oriented with their back turned to a moving robot, (especially when in close proximity).

C. Explainability

It is important to emphasize that by applying a neuro-symbolic approach in the proposed hybrid AI solution, it becomes possible to achieve more detailed explanations of the results returned by the system.

For the detection of a human pose example (i.e., "both hands raised"), the detection rule is a straightforward logical conjunction (AND) that determines whether both the left and right hands are raised high (the logic is shown inside the grey box in the diagram above). Each of these symbolic inputs is derived from a neural network response and is therefore associated with a probability. These probabilities propagate through the rules, enabling the computation of the overall probability that both hands are raised.

Thanks to this rule-based system, we can rollback the decision, meaning we can trace back which probabilistic symbols led to a specific outcome. This is visible in the lower part of the diagram, where we can observe which symbols were activated within the rule. Additionally, we have information from the image-level explanation. Since we know that the detected objects are hands, we can easily query the backbone network to understand why it considers the hands to be raised and, more importantly, where in the image they are located.

This approach enhances interpretability and allows us to verify whether the network is actually focusing on the correct regions when assessing hand positions.

⁶<https://github.com/ML-KULeuven/deepproblog>

⁷Y. Shen, A. Choi, and A. Darwiche, "Tractable operations for arithmetic circuits of probabilistic models," in *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, vol. 29, D. Lee, M. Sugiyama, U. Luxburg, I. Guyon, and R. Garnett, Eds. Curran Associates, Inc., 2016

Fig. 8. The contrast between the quality of blackbox explanations and the hybrid AI approach.

Furthermore, the skeletal representation provides additional context for understanding the observed behavior.

As it is shown in the figure above, the proposed approach can achieve better quality in explaining pixel-level explanations. It is particularly vivid when compared with post-hoc explainers like LIME.

VI. EXPERIMENTS

In this section, we present the results for various performance aspects affecting KPIs. In all subsections, we used a similar approach: for the test recordings, the analysis area was divided based on cameras, as illustrated in the diagram below. We have three cameras, each capturing footage that includes two to three people working alongside robots, which are labelled with the acronyms UR10 and AMR.

During the evaluation, the video stream was divided into frames at a rate of 2 frames per second. This allowed us to capture key movement changes, whether of people or robots. Based on this, individual detections for specific objects/events/situations/anomalies were counted.

A. Sensitivity and specificity of human detection

Within the use case framework, a high precision means that nearly all detected individuals are truly humans, a key factor in preventing unnecessary system interruptions due to false positives. Depending on the context and the system’s criticality, a precision level of 95% in human detection is generally considered acceptable.

To maintain these performance assumptions, the F1 score should similarly be around 95% or higher.

Camera	Recall	Specificity
Workshop Area: WS2_TA2	98.5%	99.8%
Transportation Area 1: TA1_WS2	100%	99.8%
Transportation Area 2: TA2_WS2	99.5%	100%

TABLE I
HUMAN DETECTION SENSITIVITY AND SPECIFICITY FOR DIFFERENT CAMERAS

To ensure a fair analysis, we treated the human detection problem separately for each camera. The results for each camera are presented in the table above. Two metrics were considered for the cameras. As shown, for cameras 2 and 3, the expected detection rates were achieved, with Specificity and Recall exceeding 99

However, for camera WS2_TA2, which covers the workshop area where the UR10 is located, the Recall was below 99%. This is due to the fact, that part of the human work sequence is captured by a second camera because the worker disappears from the field of view in the first camera. Nevertheless, part of his body remains visible within the frame.

The failure to detect a person in camera WS2_TA2, while assuming a Recall value above 99%, does not pose a significant blocker for the proposed method in achieving the target KPIs. This is because the approach assumes that employee tracking is based on information from all cameras. In this case, the worker continues to be tracked using camera TA1_WS2.

B. Accuracy of human position/presence detection

This section takes into account both the distance between the human and the manipulator as well as their separation. This obviously projects onto various events that are detected by the hybrid AI solution. In this case, the most relevant event will be the moment when the human operator enters the restricted area where the robot manipulator (UR10) is operating.

It is important to note that this problem is doubly, if not triply, complex. First, it requires precise detection to determine that a human is present in the image. Then, it demands accurate 3D reconstruction, which essentially involves regressing multiple factors: the person’s position, pose, orientation relative to the camera, and their 3D location within a global coordinate system. All these conditions must be met to confirm that a person is present in a specific area.

In table below we demonstrate the performance scores for the event indicated as “HUMAN IN ROBOT WORKING AREA”.

	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
Human in a Safe Zone	1.00	1.00	1.00
Human in Robot Working Area	0.97	0.97	0.97
Accuracy			0.99
Macro avg	0.99	0.99	0.99
Weighted avg	0.99	0.99	0.99

TABLE II
EVENT: HUMAN_IN_ROBOT_WORKING_AREA
PERFORMANCE METRICS.

In order to visualize the moments where the solution fails in correctly spotting the moment of human entering the restricted zone, we have obtained some examples of false and negatives:

- due to the occlusion and motion blur the reconstructed skeletons are a bit inaccurate causing detection error,
- due to inaccuracies in depth measurements, the posture appears closer to the camera causing the false alarm.

C. Accuracy of distance measurements

Measuring the distance between different parts of the worker’s body and the robot’s arm depends on multiple factors, such as the worker’s posture, positioning

Fig. 9. Example outputs from cameras (including robots' acronyms) and their naming.

relative to the camera, and distance from the camera. All these factors influence measurement precision. In this use case, the camera is positioned directly above the workshop where the worker collaborates with the robot. Using this camera setup, we conducted an experiment to evaluate the expected accuracy of human-robot distance measurements. We focus only on these parts of the video recording where the worker's hands are visible.

In the considered experiment, we focused on a close-up recording capturing the collaboration between a human and a robot. The video sequence records a worker manipulating their hands while assembling a PCB. In this portion of the recording, we can clearly track hand movements and count relevant detection errors. The footage also shows the movements of the UR10 robotic arm, which delivers components to the worker.

For the selected sequence, the locations where the human hand should be detected were manually annotated. To facilitate this process, the video sequence was split into individual frames, sampled at approximately 1 to 2 frames per second. Given the precise hand movements during assembly, this approach helped avoid redundant images that would have occurred with a higher frame rate. As a result, roughly 400 frames were extracted for the considered video sequence.

We approach this problem as a classification task, meaning we assess how often the system correctly determines that specific skeletal points or body parts of the human are within a given distance. We set a threshold of 20 cm. Apart from the frames containing the worker, we also included frames where the worker is not present in the designated working area (those have been indicated as 1 and 0 in the table below).

Class	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
YES	0.92	0.93	0.92
NO	0.98	0.97	0.97
Accuracy			0.96
Macro Avg	0.95	0.95	0.95
Weighted Avg	0.96	0.96	0.96

TABLE III

HAND PRESENCE DETECTION WITHIN A 20CM RANGE FROM GROUND TRUTH: CLASSIFICATION METRICS.

From the table above, we can conclude that 97% of the trials fall within the expected 20cm accuracy range from the ground truth. Naturally, this accuracy will

significantly deteriorate when workers are observed from a greater distance.

In this analysis, we focused solely on the workshop, where the worker is positioned close enough for depth perception to allow fairly accurate measurements, with a granularity better than 20cm. The issue of distance and occlusion becomes more pronounced in the next section, where the worker in TA1 (Transportation Area) is captured in a side profile to the camera, causing their hands to be frequently occluded.

D. Accuracy of anomaly (events types) detection

In this section, we present an evaluation of the performance of event and anomaly detection, as well as events categorization capabilities. For testing purposes, we used an annotated dataset to assess various classification metrics, including Precision, Recall, and F1-score. The dataset focuses on events (concerning workers and robots) such as Band, Human in Robot Working Area, Squatting, Waving, Both Arms Up, Left Arm Up, Right Arm Up, and T-Pose.

The following tables provide detailed information on the values of these performance metrics. For the T-Pose, we achieved a very high Precision of 100%. However, the Recall in this case was around 90-92%, which, in terms of balanced accuracy, resulted in an overall performance of 95%.

Class	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
Something Else	1.00	1.00	1.00
T-POSE	1.00	0.90	0.95
Accuracy			1.00
Macro Avg	1.00	0.95	0.97
Weighted Avg	1.00	1.00	1.00

TABLE IV

T-POSE EVENT CLASSIFICATION METRICS

For the LH_UP (left hand up) event, the balanced accuracy reached 92%. This was due to a slightly lower Precision of 92% and a Recall of 85%. The issue of reduced Recall was primarily due to challenges in the Transportation Area, where the model struggled to accurately recognize raised hands when a person was at a significant distance from the camera.

For the Right Arm Up event, the occlusion problem proved to be even more impactful. This was because tasks such as loading and organizing items in the Transportation Area were often performed using the right hand. This issue is evident, while the hand

Class	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
Something Else	1.00	1.00	1.00
LH_UP	0.92	0.85	0.88
Accuracy			0.99
Macro Avg	0.96	0.92	0.94
Weighted Avg	0.99	0.99	0.99

TABLE V
LH_UP EVENT CLASSIFICATION METRICS

appears above the head, the rest of the arm is largely occluded by the worker’s body, making it difficult for the model to correctly identify the gesture.

Class	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
Something Else	1.00	0.99	0.99
RH_UP	0.62	0.71	0.67
Accuracy			0.99
Macro Avg	0.81	0.85	0.83
Weighted Avg	0.99	0.99	0.99

TABLE VI
RH_UP EVENT CLASSIFICATION METRICS

Regarding the Hi-Gesture (waving gesture), it appeared very rarely in the entire dataset. Only a few frames were successfully extracted from the full recording. As shown in the tables, the system managed to detect over 80% of these frames. However, the model also produced several false positives, leading to a significantly lower precision compared to previous events. False detections occurred when a person was standing with their back to the camera and had a slightly raised hand (e.g. adjusting hair) or when the hand was completely covered by the rest of the body.

Class	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
Something Else	1.00	1.00	1.00
Hi Gesture / Wave	0.56	0.83	0.67
Accuracy			0.99
Macro Avg	0.78	0.91	0.83
Weighted Avg	1.00	0.99	1.00

TABLE VII
HI_GESTURE EVENT CLASSIFICATION METRICS

For the Both Arms Up gesture, the classification metrics are significantly better. The balanced accuracy reached 92%, with precision also exceeding 90% and recall at 85%.

Class	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
Something Else	0.98	0.99	0.99
LRH_UP	0.93	0.85	0.89
Accuracy			0.97
Macro Avg	0.95	0.92	0.94
Weighted Avg	0.97	0.97	0.97

TABLE VIII
LRH_UP EVENT CLASSIFICATION METRICS

For the Squat event (e.g. to pick up a dropped object) the balanced accuracy reached 86%. However, there was a higher false positive rate, which led to a decrease in precision. This issue primarily materialized because the squat movement was difficult to distinguish from the bend activity, especially when part of

the legs was slightly occluded by the robot’s arm or was outside the camera’s field of view.

Class	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
Something Else	1.00	1.00	1.00
Squat	0.62	0.71	0.67
Accuracy			0.99
Macro Avg	0.81	0.86	0.83
Weighted Avg	0.99	0.99	0.99

TABLE IX
SQUAT EVENT CLASSIFICATION METRICS.

For detecting the bent activity, the main challenge was identifying whether the person’s silhouette was actually bent, especially when they were far from the camera and moving toward it. This made it difficult to determine the posture accurately. Additionally, mis-detections occurred when the gesture was in its early stage, or the person was partially outside the camera’s field of view.

Class	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
Something Else	0.99	1.00	1.00
Bent	1.00	0.58	0.74
Accuracy			0.99
Macro Avg	1.00	0.79	0.87
Weighted Avg	0.99	0.99	0.99

TABLE X
BENT EVENT CLASSIFICATION METRICS.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

The presented Hybrid AI solution enhances the trustworthiness of anomaly and event detection by improving explainability, robustness, safety, performance transparency, and rare event detection. By combining deep learning-based “perception” with probabilistic symbolic reasoning, we enable a more interpretable, reliable, and human-centric AI system. We particularly focus on human-robot collaboration and critical safety applications. More precisely, the proposed system contributes to AI trustworthiness in several key areas and aspects:

- Explainability through Neuro-symbolic Reasoning. Traditional deep learning models function as black boxes, providing highly accurate but often difficult to interpret results. By incorporating probabilistic symbolic reasoning, our Hybrid AI approach allows decisions to be “rolled back”, tracing the probabilistic symbols that led to specific classifications. As shown in “event detection scenarios”, symbolic representations enable rule-based reasoning, making the decision-making process more transparent. This interpretability helps users verify the AI’s focus points (e.g., ensuring that the system correctly detects relevant image areas).
- Robustness Against Occlusion and Ambiguity. One of the challenges in event detection is handling occlusions, varying camera perspectives, and ambiguities. We currently combat this problem using additional rules that will eliminate

- given camera as a source of reliable prediction when the occlusion is expected to be significant.
- **Enhanced Safety and Human-Robot Collaboration.** In Human-Robot Collaboration (HRC) reliable event detection is essential to prevent accidents and ensure safe interactions is important. The proposed approach addresses this by: (i) detecting human presence and actions (e.g., detecting a human in the robot's working area), (ii) identifying critical gestures such as T-Pose or Both Arms Up (which may indicate emergency signals or predefined collaborative actions), (iii) reducing uncertainty in classification by leveraging probabilistic rules.
 - **Trust via Performance Metrics and Error Analysis.** In our work, we measure classification accuracy using classical metrics such as a precision, recall, and f1-score for different events and KPI-related aspects. Moreover, we transparently analyze common failure cases, causes by occlusions or motion blur, to possibly guide further improvements. Moreover, we also interpret model decisions using an image-level explanation approach, to verify the visual evidence supporting a classification.
 - **Reliability in Rare Event Detection.** Rare events exhibit a challenge due to the limited number of training samples. Our approach allows extracting probabilistic features improving recall in underrepresented gestures and expressing them by mean of probabilistic rules.

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